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Research Article

**COMMON SIDE EFFECTS AND LEADING CAUSE OF
DISCONTINUATION OF METHOTREXATE IN
RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS PATIENTS**Dr Sidra Shaheen¹, Dr Sahrish Batool², Dr Muhammad Zulqarnain³^{1,3} THQ Hospital Sahiwal District Sargodha² THQ Hospital Jaranwala, Faisalabad

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Abstract:

Aim: To evaluate frequency and to identify factors which may increase the discontinuation of Methotrexate (MTX) among Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) patients.

Place and Duration: In the Rheumatology Department of Fatima Memorial Hospital, Lahore for one year duration from March 2019 to February 2020.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted in the Rheumatology Department of Fatima Memorial Hospital, Lahore in subjects that are currently or previously were using MTX. All the patients were included who fulfilled the 1987 revised American Rheumatism Association criteria for classification of RA. Medical records for 200 RA patients were chosen through convenience method then they reviewed

Results: The study involved 200 RA patients, 169 (84.5%) were women, 31 (15.5%) were men. Their age is between 12 and 80 years, on average 45.07 and standard deviation 14.37 years. Approximately 67 (33.5%) patients stated that the disease duration was 10 years and more, and 147 (73.5%) patients used MTX and 53 (26.5%) did not use the drug. 24 of 147 patients (27%) did not receive MTX regularly for various reasons. The most common side effects are abdominal pain, laziness and dizziness. There is no statistically significant relationship between sex, education level, duration of illness and interval $p = 0.05$.

Conclusion: The study showed a low rate of discontinuation due to side effects, MTX appears to be a safe drug for long-term use in RA patients. More attempts should be made to minimize side effects and discontinuation of MTX to obtain the benefits of a cornerstone drug in the treatment of RA.

Key words: Arthritis, Rheumatoid, Methotrexate, Rheumatic diseases

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INTRODUCTION:

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is one of the most common chronic inflammation that causes systemic diseases and pain, swelling and joint damage. It affects about 0.5-1% of the world population. It is characterized by inflammation of the synovial tissue, which, if left untreated, leads to permanent structural damage, and ultimately to long-term disability and poor quality of life¹⁻². RA is one of the conditions in which patients should take medication every day to relieve pain and reduce the risk of physical disability³⁻⁴. The use of traditional and biological disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (DMARDs) improves the result, provides good control and protects the disease. DMARDs are the basis of RA treatment. Methotrexate (MTX) is the most commonly used DMARD in RA with less toxicity and better tolerance than others. Due to its antagonistic effect on folic acid metabolism, it is classified as a pharmacological metabolite. Although the mechanism by which MTX at a low dose modulates inflammation in RA is still uncertain, evidence of its effectiveness has been well documented in several randomized controlled trials (RCTs) and meta-analyses⁵⁻⁶. The safety profile of MTX has been studied over 25 years with very few clinically significant adverse events at low weekly doses used to treat RA⁷. MTX courses show the longest indicators in clinical medicine in terms of both their effectiveness and safety. The safety profile of MTX indicates that it belongs to the safest agents used to treat any arthritis. It is known that 80% of all DMARDs are suspended for up to 2 years after starting treatment due to adverse effects or ineffectiveness, with the exception of methotrexate (MTX), which has been widely used for over 5 years⁸⁻⁹. Many patients give up medication at the doctor's disposal, while others give up because they experience undesirable side effects. In a multicentre retrospective study involving 760 RA patients who analyzed the causes of DMARD withdrawal, treatment was discontinued in 47.1%, 43.2% and 9% due to lack of efficacy, adverse events or unspecified causes, respectively. The study aims to determine the frequency and factors that may increase discontinuation of MTX treatment in our RA patients.

METHODS:

It is based on a retrospective analysis that reviews the medical records of patients using MTX or

previous rheumatoid arthritis (RA). We conducted a cross-sectional study that currently or previously uses MTX. All enrolled patients met the revised 1987 American Rheumatic Society criteria regarding RA classification and age above 12 years. Medical records of 200 RA patients were selected using the adequacy method and subjected to analysis and analysis. The process of not destroying information and embezzling used patients requires harming patients and protecting patient confidentiality. The study included two pages for data collection; The first includes the number of medical records of RA patients, and each file will have a specific code number and will be saved with the mentor. The second page will contain the following information: gender, age, level of education, duration of illness, use of MTX and compliance with use of MTX. To identify the causes of the combined lake (side effects, what is it, inefficiency). Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21. Data were summarized using descriptive statistics: mean $\pm$ standard deviation (SD) or frequency (number) and percentage (%). The T-test and chi-square test were used respectively. A probability value of $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

The study involved 200 patients with rheumatoid arthritis according to the changed ACR classification criteria for RA. About 169 (84.5%) of our patients were women and 31 (15.5%) were men. The age ranges from 12 to 80 years, on average 45.07 years, and standard deviation 14.37 years. About 70 (35%) participants were illiterate, 46 (23%) study participants could read and write, 38 (19%) were in high school, and 46 (23%) were in tertiary, master or university education, while having a degree, the majority of study participants were 728 graduates (66.9%) (Table 1). The duration of the disease ranged from six months to over 10 years; 5 (2.5%) disease duration less than 6 months, 35 (17.5%) duration from 6 months to two years, 42 patients (21%) disease duration from 2 to 5 years, 51 (25, 5%) patients from 5 years to 9 years, in 67 (33.5) the duration of the disease was 10 or more. Our 147 (73.5%) patients did not use methotrexate and 53 (26.5%) MTX. In 107 (53.5) patients, apart from doctors, there was another source of information; 82.2% received information from the Internet (Chart 1).

Table 1 General characteristics of RA patients

Variables	N (%)
Gender	
Male	31 (15.5)
Female	169 (84.5)
Age (years)	
Mean $\pm$ SD	45.07 $\pm$ 14.37
Educational level	
Illiterate	70 (35)
Can read and write	46 (23)
High school	38 (19)
University graduated	45 (22.5)
Advanced studies	1 (0.5)
Duration of disease	
Less than 6 months	5 (2.5)
From 6 months - 2 years	35 (17.5)
From 2 - 5 years	42 (21)
From 5 - 9 years	51 (25.5)
Above 10 years	67 (33.5)
MTX used	
Yes	147 (73.5)
No	53 (26.5)

147 patients; 24 of them (27%) did not receive MTX regularly for various reasons, as shown in Table 2, 19 (12.9%) are concerned about the side effects of MTX patients, 8 (5.4%) believe that MTX does not work the same way as ready MTX (poor response), and 6 (4.1%) patients were not regular. MTX was not available.

Table 2 Causes of methotrexate (MTX) Irregular used in 24 patients

Cause	N	%
Forgot	4	16.7
Side effects	9	37.5
Not useful	1	4.2
Afraid of side effects	5	20.8
Finished of MTX tablets	4	16.7
Unavailable	5	20.8
Price	1	4.2

Side effects of MTX are shown in Table 3. Nausea and vomiting were detected in 21 (14.3) patients; abdominal pain was detected in 29 (19.7%) patients; laziness and laziness 29 (19.7%); Microbial infection was detected in 10 patients (6.8%) and 7 patients (4.8%) had joint pain.

Table 3 MTX associated in 147 patients with RA

Side effect	N	%
Nausea and vomiting	21	14.3
Stomach ache	29	19.7
Indolence and sloth	29	19.7
Microbial infections	10	6.8
Severe headache	1	0.7
Hair loss	2	1.4
Breathing problems	2	1.4
Vision problems	2	1.4
Joints pains	7	4.8

Table 4 shows that there is no significant relationship between the chi-square test, education level and duration of sex, and the irregular cause of the age test ($P > 0.05$).

Table 4 Comparison of MTX regular and non-regular patients by demographic variables

Variables		MTX regular				P
		Yes (146)		No (54)		
		N	%	N	%	
Age (years)	Mean $\pm$ SD	46.06 $\pm$ 14.13	-	39.96 $\pm$ 12.87	-	0.054
Sex	Male	20	95.2	1	4.8	0.138
	Female	103	81.7	23	18.3	
Education	Non-educated	40	81.6	9	18.4	0.58
	Can read and write	29	87.9	4	12.1	
	High school	24	80	6	20	
	University graduated	29	85.3	5	14.7	
	Advanced studies	1	100	0	0	
Duration	Less than 6 months	3	100	0	0	0.934
	From 6 months to two years	23	79.3	6	20.7	
	From 2 - 5 years	27	87.1	4	12.9	
	From 5 - 9 years	31	81.6	7	18.4	
	Above 10 years	39	84.8	7	15.2	

DISCUSSION:

In this study, which involved 200 RA patients, including 147 (73.5%) patients, MTX was still present, 24 patients (16.3%) stopped MTX for various reasons¹¹⁻¹². This result differs from those reported on the MTX release rate, with a gap of 37% after about 6 years, about 45% after about 8 years and about 29.3%. About 80% discontinuation or lack of efficacy due to negative effects when comparing MTX as a safe and effective drug,

especially when compared to those reported in other DMARDs in the first 2 years. Our patients' reasons for discontinuing MTX include the first side effects (9; 37.5%) and fear of side effects (5; 20.8%), including nausea and vomiting, and abdominal pain. Side effects are a common factor in checking the regular use of MTX, this result is compatible with it. The most common side effects were more than in other studies (53%) than in the gastrointestinal tract (53.7%) and the Indian study (21%). These include

nausea, vomiting, stomach ache as well as laziness and laziness¹³⁻¹⁴. According to the Narenjo scale [20], absolutely no MTX-related side effects can be mentioned. However, no adverse effects were irreversible. Comparing patients in group 1 (regularly using MTX) with patients in group 2 (using MTX irregularly) using the Chi square test, a statistically significant relationship; We didn't find any relevant statistics regarding disease duration, level of education or gender. Vomiting and nausea were significant and statistically related to two groups ($p = 0.004$). The main limitation of this study is that most RA patients are subjective and almost all patients take other medications, and the retrospective pattern of our study is another limitation¹⁵.

CONCLUSION:

As a result, given the relatively low discontinuation rate due to side effects, MTX appears to be a safe drug for long-term use in RA patients. More attempts should be made to minimize side effects and discontinuation of MTX to achieve the benefits of a cornerstone drug in the treatment of RA.

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